

Ethical-Aesthetic Convergences in Ecologically Oriented Electroacoustic Practices

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Abstract

This paper examines the convergence of ethical and aesthetic frameworks in electroacoustic practices shaped by ecological awareness. It begins by addressing how the semiotic richness of recorded sound—central to the interdisciplinary nature of electroacoustic music—has encouraged composers to engage with philosophical and scientific discourses on perception, environment, and alterity. Drawing on traditions such as the GRM and the World Soundscape Project, the paper traces how figures including François Bayle and Luc Ferrari, alongside more recent practitioners such as Toshiya Tsunoda, Anne F. Jacques, and Diane Barbé, have employed sound recording to articulate situated and relational perspectives. These practices reveal a perceptual ethics informed by phenomenology (Merleau-Ponty) and early ecological thought (von Uexküll), challenging modernist notions of aesthetic autonomy. Instead, they reclaim aesthetics in its original sense—as *aisthesis*, the embodied practice of perception—proposing a compositional approach grounded in attentive listening, ecological sensitivity, and the politics of sonic engagement within an increasingly interdependent world.

1. Introduction

Electroacoustic practices have historically constituted a site of interdisciplinary experimentation, offering fertile ground for encounters among philosophy, linguistics, technology, psychology, acoustics, and beyond. This hybridity renders the field resistant to univocal definitions—and equally resistant to any attempt at disentangling its constitutive components. Despite recurrent efforts by composers, researchers, and theorists to delineate coherent aesthetic frameworks or to impose retrospective taxonomies, electroacoustic practices continually overflow such boundaries.

This paper does not seek to resolve these debates or to reduce the field to a single perspective. Rather, it aims to identify a *fil rouge* running through a number of post-Schaefferian and contemporary experiences grounded in sound recording, tracing how they collectively reveal a broader orientation within the electroacoustic domain: a turn toward the construction of tools and modes of engagement for exploring, understanding, and re-orienting our relation to reality—rather than toward the production of self-enclosed, solipsistic works of art.

To articulate this tendency, I draw on semiotic theory—specifically on the definition of signification as the correlation between expression and content (Eco 1975/2008, Hjelmslev 1961, Marrone 2018)—together with elements of phenomenology and the science of perception. Through this combined lens, recorded sound emerges not as a mere representational medium but as a relational device: a means of mediating encounters between perceiving

subjects and their environments. The ethical dimension of this relationality, though not universal across all practices, can be understood as a natural extension of such phenomenological openness—a responsiveness to the alterity that sound both reveals and enacts.

In order to understand how such a relational orientation manifests within electroacoustic practice, it is useful to look at the phenomenological foundations that continue to inform the ways we record, compose, and listen. Pierre Schaeffer's work, despite its "reduction-based" methodology, reveals a deeper intuition: that listening is never neutral but always a mode of engagement, an embodied and situated act through which the world discloses itself. It is precisely this tension—between abstraction and engagement—that many subsequent electroacoustic practices inherit and reinterpret.

From this perspective, Merleau-Ponty's notion of behaviour and desire offers a powerful lens: perception is not a passive reception of stimuli but an active exploration, driven by our bodily orientation and our attraction toward the world. Sound recording and manipulation thus become not mere technical procedures but expressions of this same intentional movement—the composer's or listener's desire to reach out, to grasp, to reconfigure the sonic field as a way of knowing and relating. Meaning arises not just from representation but from participation, i.e. how sound mediates between self and environment. It is along this axis—where behaviour and desire inform both the act of listening and the act of composing—that the phenomenological, the semiotic, and the ethical converge, giving certain electroacoustic practices their distinctive capacity to explore and reorient our being-in-the-world.

2. Post-schaefferian practices between perception, relation and meaning

Much has been written about the phenomenological grounding of Schaeffer's research and of many electroacoustic practices based on recorded sound, as well as about the peculiar ability of recorded sound to reference a source—though not necessarily its *actual* source (Chion 2009, 24-30)—and to evoke images drawn from the listener's experience of the real world. The relationship between sound in its phenomenological dimension and meaning lies at the core of Schaeffer's *Traité des objets musicaux* (TOM). As several scholars and Nattiez (1990, 94) above all have observed, the correlation between these two domains in the TOM is arguably reductive in certain respects; nonetheless, Schaeffer's work establishes the theoretical foundations for an entire field that places the interplay between perception, *morphé*, and signification at its centre. His attempt to connect multiple disciplines through artistic research resonates strongly in subsequent developments, and its most direct legacy is undoubtedly acousmatic music.

Far from being a simple rebranding of *musique concrète*, acousmatic music adopts a twofold theoretical stance. On the one hand, it positions itself as a genre within the broader electroacoustic field, thereby progressively relinquishing the universalist ambitions of the avant-garde. On the other, it explicitly foregrounds the relation between phenomenological listening and processes of signification, making this interplay a defining aspect of its identity. As Bayle openly states:

With this term—which goes beyond both electronic and electroacoustic—I want to designate those musics that go beyond their own sonic indices, their instrumental

causes, and that engage an active listening concerned with effects and with meaning (Bayle 1993, 37).

For Bayle, listening is an active encounter in which perceptual experience and meaning-making converge: sound is recognised as having an inherent sense while also prompting the attribution of further significance (ibidem, 37–38). This superimposition of perceptual and interpretive levels transforms the work into a mechanism of signification whose pivotal concept is the *sound image*, an object of perception similar to the sound object but founded on representation-through-sound rather than repeated listening:

[...] by introducing representation rather than repetition, the sound image attains the status of sign, due to the (significant) fact that between the (physical) cause and its (phenomenological) effect a form is interposed. [...] This operational faculty functions through the intersection of a space of ideas projected onto a world of realization. (Bayle 1993, 50)

The sound image extends the path traced by Schaeffer: drawing selectively on Peircean semiotics, Bayle attributes a renewed role to the listener, who actively constructs meaning within the perceptual encounter. Recorded sound thus becomes a medium through which the listener can trace a path back to the world: a mediated form that sustains relational presence even as it is transformed. Musically, this shift is evident. Bayle frequently juxtaposes synthesised “pure” forms with recorded sounds that unmistakably reveal their source—inviting reverie, associative movement, and occasionally a renewed awareness of the environments from which these sounds emerge. This is the case in *Smorzando* from *Sept préludes (Camera Oscura)*, where high-pitched synthetic tones glide over the reverberant bouncing of a ping-pong ball; or in the striking elevator sounds in *Tremblement de terre très doux*, which function as both gestural elements and meaningful signs of descent into material depth. In *Jêita*, recordings from the eponymous cave interact with synthetic material, evoking the place that inspired the composition and contributing to a strong sense of site-specific reference. In this respect, Bayle anticipates what is now common among soundscape-informed artists: recording *in situ* in order to compose works that remain perceptually and imaginatively tied to the environments from which they arise.

This relational dynamic acquires a distinctive form in Bernard Parmegiani’s work, where the interplay between the artificial and the natural becomes a fundamental axis of his aesthetic dialectic. This has been well documented in the poietic analysis conducted by Mion, Nattiez and Thomas (1983) of *De Natura Sonorum* (DNS). Yet Parmegiani’s approach differs from Bayle’s in its emphasis on the material continuity of sound: synthetic and environmental materials transform into one another, keeping open the perceptual link between listener and world despite aesthetic manipulation. In *Dedans Dehors*, conceived as a sequel to DNS, Parmegiani intensifies this exploration of perceptual boundaries and material identity. The second section of the piece is especially representative of this approach. Here, the sound of a water droplet is placed in dialogue with a synthetic counterpart that attempts to imitate it—a gesture both deliberate and designed to be recognised as such. While grounded in a morphological analysis of the natural sound and its artificial replica, and on a musical pacing that keeps the tradition meaningful, the passage relies on a clear mechanism of signification prepared by the sound of a watery wave, introduced not only for its *morphé*—its energetic unfolding that closes the gesture which interrupts the ostinato electronic flux of the first section—but also for its semantic charge. It unmistakably signifies “water,” situating the listener in relation to a familiar element and establishing the frame through which the ensuing “dance of water drops” acquires perceptual coherence and worldly grounding. The artificial and

the natural are thus not opposing categories but poles within a continuous negotiation—one that subtly reasserts our embeddedness within material and environmental processes.

A similar orientation can be found in the British acousmatic tradition, which, following Parmegiani, frequently explores the dialogue between natural and artificial sound materials, often developing it into the broader dialectic of the real and the unreal. One well-known example is the sudden emergence of bagpipe recordings from within the dense texture of Denis Smalley's *Pentes*; another is the more recent Jonty Harrison's *Afterthought*, where recordings of a calm private garden are gradually traversed by manipulations, intrusions, and augmented fragments of perception—an acousmatic rendering of a half-sleep state in which things are no longer exactly what they are. In Harrison's case, however, the strategy does not rely solely on morphology or designation, but on the transmission of a sense of place—a situated, affective experience of environment whose transformations nevertheless retain a perceptual tie to the world they evoke.

In this case, Harrison's approach is clearly informed by soundscape composition, which is itself grounded in the interplay between perception and meaning described above. In *The Tuning of the World*, Murray Schafer acknowledges the value of Schaeffer's method (1977: 130), yet urges researchers not to confine their practice to analysis alone. For Schafer, explicit reference to sound sources is not a limitation but a central methodological and aesthetic principle. In this perspective, recorded sound functions as a trace: it does not merely document a sonic event but preserves a perceptual link to the environment from which it derives. A recording thus becomes more than a means of reproduction; it becomes a medium of reconnection, re-opening a relation to the places and situations that shaped the sound.

Before Schafer, the work that most forcefully pursued this direction was undoubtedly Luc Ferrari's *Presque Rien*, where the trace not only reconnects the listener to the depicted bay but also draws attention to the very medium that allows such an encounter to occur. Brian Kane (2014, 132) has argued that the technological medium is the true and only object of *Presque Rien*, noting that "Ferrari [...] brings the recorded character of the recording to the fore." Yet Ferrari's initial impulse was grounded in an encounter with a specific environment and its quietness: a moment of attention, awakening, and situated listening. What is beautiful in the *Presque Rien*, Ferrari observes, is that *things make themselves noticed* (Warburton, 1998) - not the recording and what it conceptually represents as a device but things, small details and sounds which are of the world. The will to record arises from the experience of place: from being there, listening into its unfolding, and wanting more. This attraction seems to be driven in Ferrari by sincere and spontaneous *desire*, an attitude towards the world that, as we will see in the next paragraph, resonates well with Merleau-Ponty's conception of intentionality and behavior; an attitude that also drives a sense of *care* towards the world that seems to genuinely animate Ferrari's entire body of works and can easily be recognized in many works where sound - and what it takes and represents - is treated with the utmost respect.

What emerges from these post-Schaefferian practices is that recorded sound consistently operates as a site of relational listening: it maintains a perceptual tie between listener and world, even when transformed, abstracted, or displaced. This relationality—grounded in place, environment, and embodied attention—quietly anticipates the ecological orientations that will structure the final part of this paper. If acousmatic music has long relied on the interplay between perception and signification, the crucial question becomes how such a relation is established in the first place. This directs our attention to the act of recording itself, and to the microphone as the primary technological extension of perception—a device that not only

captures sound but actively shapes the modes through which composers and listeners enter into relation with the world.

3. Which phenomenology?

Schaeffer's phenomenology emerges from a synthesis of concepts drawn from Husserl and from the interpretations—and critiques—of Husserl advanced by later thinkers, foremost among them, as Solomos (1999) emphasises, Merleau-Ponty. While the notions of *epoché* and *reduction* remain clearly Husserlian in origin (Kane, 2014 esp. Part 1), the foundational premise of Schaeffer's project is unmistakably indebted to Merleau-Ponty's *Phénoménologie de la perception* (PP). This dual inheritance introduces a productive tension at the heart of the TOM: on the one hand, the Husserlian ambition to suspend the world in order to analyse sonic phenomena in their "pure" givenness; on the other, a Merleau-Pontian commitment to perception as embodied, situated, and already entangled with the world. The question, then, is which of these philosophical attitudes becomes dominant—and which is taken up and developed—in the post-Schaefferian practices discussed above.

As Schaeffer's work rests on several deep assumptions that align with Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology than with Husserl's transcendental project, at least three major points of convergence can be identified. First, Merleau-Ponty insists that perception precedes and grounds all other modalities of experience, including sensation: perception is not something derived later but the very condition under which sensation becomes intelligible—an idea that finds a clear counterpart in Schaeffer's own assertions in the TOM (1966, 91-94). Second, Merleau-Ponty argues that sensations never appear in isolation; they arise within a *champ perceptif*, a perceptual field already structured by orientation, expectation, and sense—an insight indebted to Gestalt theory and echoed by Schaeffer when he observes that no sound object can be apprehended outside the network of perceptual relations that give it form (1966, 274). Third, and crucially for the relational implications of sonic practice, Merleau-Ponty reconceives intersubjectivity through the notion of the *alter ego*: another embodied subject who appears to me within the same world and whose presence reveals the limits of my own self-coincidence. This position resonates with Schaeffer's reflections on the inevitability of other perceptual perspectives (Schaeffer 1966, 264–265). This final point is particularly revealing, for Merleau-Ponty's conception of alterity seems to surface within the TOM almost despite Schaeffer's limited explicit interest in intersubjectivity. Yet it becomes, implicitly, a structural necessity: if Schaeffer aims to articulate a sharable knowledge of perceived sonic phenomena, then the existence of other listening subjects—and of their possible perspectives—must be presupposed. As Merleau-Ponty writes:

[...] for the Other not to be an empty word, it is necessary that my existence never be reduced to the consciousness I have of existing, but that it also involve the consciousness others may have of me—and therefore my incarnation in a nature and at least the possibility of a historical situation. (1945/2010, 662–663)

Or, in an even more explicit formulation:

[...] we must no longer conceive consciousness as a constituting consciousness, as a pure being-for-itself, but as a perceptual consciousness—as the subject of a behaviour, as being-in-the-world or existence—for only in this way can the Other appear to me at the summit of his phenomenal body and acquire a kind of 'locality' (1945/2010, 1052).

This Merleau-Pontian conception of perception as relational and embodied is precisely what survives within Schaeffer's project even where his own theoretical ambitions appear to move in the opposite direction. For although Schaeffer often pushes toward an abstraction of sounds from the world—seeking an ontology of sound “beyond” sound, in a quasi-idealistic frame—his system cannot escape the perceptual ground on which it rests. Reduced listening may aspire to suspend reference, but it presupposes the primacy of perception that Merleau-Ponty describes. One cannot perform reduction without first encountering sound as something that appears, that solicits attention, that emerges within a field of sense. In attempting to bracket the world, Schaeffer inadvertently reveals the depth of our relation to it: the world returns as what must be suspended, and therefore as what is already there. An attitude confirmed by Schaeffer's idea that music carries sense - if not meaning-, and acts as a communication medium.

What Schaeffer's successors inherit and share, therefore, is not the idealist aspiration to comprehend sound beyond sound, but the procedural acknowledgement that listening is relational—that the sonic object, however abstracted, arises from an embodied perceptual situation. Ferrari, Bayle, Parmegiani, and the British acousmatic composers all take up this relational premise, redirecting it away from Schaeffer's bracketed neutrality and toward a renewed engagement with the world. They reactivate the Merleau-Pontian core: perception as a mode of being-with, and sound as a site where the world appears not as neutral data but as a partner in an unfolding relation. This is what makes Schaeffer “Schaeffer-proof”: what allows his work to remain generative for practices increasingly oriented toward situatedness, world-relations, and—eventually—ecological thinking.

It is precisely along this existential and relational line of thought—where perception is understood as the body's mode of being-in-the-world—that Schaeffer's legacy becomes most fruitful for contemporary electroacoustic practices. For if perception is always already situational, embodied, and world-directed, then the act of recording is not a neutral capture of sonic data but an extension of this intentional relation. The microphone, in this perspective, becomes a technical prolongation of embodied perception: it orients attention, frames encounters, and brings into relief aspects of the environment that might otherwise remain unnoticed. By mediating our perceptual openness to the world, it implicitly engages the conditions of our embeddedness within it—conditions that later practices will explore more explicitly in ecological, both perceptual and ethical, terms.

It is therefore unsurprising that composers such as the already mentioned Harrison, as well as Å. Parmerud, H. Tutschku, N. Barrett, and many others, have readily integrated overtly relational elements—voices, street recordings, environmental soundscapes—into their compositional languages. Their practices resonate with the ecological orientation that the World Soundscape Project systematized both ideologically and analytically: a listening that foregrounds context, environment, and the relational situatedness of the sonic event. Across these examples, the microphone remains the common mediating element. It is the device that enables these relational visions to be shared—the instrument through which perceptual openness becomes communicable. Far from being a passive tool, the microphone functions as a hinge between embodied perception and the world it encounters, amplifying, translating, and transmitting the very relational stance that underlies these practices. Born as a technological imitation of the ear, it soon becomes its extension and counterpart, proposing a complementary—and at times externalising—perspective on our perceptual engagement with the world.

4. Sound as ecological means: on the microphone mediation

Building on what has just been established, we may now consider the broader implications of the Merleau-Pontian orientation that underlies many recording-based sound practices. Merleau-Ponty's existential phenomenology is deeply informed, and in part motivated, by scientific research—something clearly visible in the experimental and descriptive method of the PP. It is well known though (Ostachuk 2013; Umbelino 2013) that even before the PP, his key concept of *behaviour*—understood as an organism's active, world-directed mode of being rather than its mere spatial location—is shaped by his early engagement with Jakob von Uexküll's notion of the *Umwelt*. In *A Foray into the Worlds of Animals and Humans* (1934/2010), Uexküll provides the conceptual grounding that enables Merleau-Ponty to reconceive animal life not as a chain of mechanistic reactions but as a structured and meaningful relation to a surrounding world.

For Uexküll, the *Umwelt* is not an objective environment conceived as a neutral container of stimuli, but a subjective-relational world constituted through the perceptual and motor capacities of a living being. Each organism inhabits a world that is meaningful *for it*, structured by what Uexküll calls functional cycles: dynamic loops linking perception and action, sensing and responding, in which certain aspects of the surroundings acquire salience while others simply do not exist (1934/2010, 49). The *Umwelt* is therefore neither a mental representation nor a physical totality, but a field of significance co-emerging with the organism's way of being. What defines an *Umwelt* is not what is “there” in general, but what matters—what can be perceived, approached, avoided, or acted upon by a particular body.

Merleau-Ponty (1942/2013) radicalizes this insight by translating it into a phenomenology of behaviour. Behaviour, for him, is not a sequence of reactions triggered by external causes, nor the execution of pre-programmed responses, but the expressive manifestation of an organism's relation to its world. To behave is to take up a situation, to respond to it in a manner that is already oriented by sense. Behaviour thus names the pre-reflective intentionality through which a body inhabits its *Umwelt*: a practical, situated intelligence that precedes explicit thought and representation. Against both mechanistic physiology and intellectualist psychology, Merleau-Ponty insists that behaviour is meaningful through and through, because it unfolds within a world that is already structured as a horizon of possible actions.

Crucially, this behavioural intentionality is not closed or self-sufficient. It is animated by what Merleau-Ponty increasingly describes in terms of *désir*—a fundamental drive toward the world that cannot be reduced to biological need or functional adaptation (Merleau-Ponty, 1945/2010, esp. Part I). *Désir*, in this sense, is not the pursuit of a determinate object, but an openness toward what exceeds the subject: a tendency to reach out, to explore, to be affected. It is this desire that prevents behaviour from collapsing into mere adjustment to a given milieu. The organism does not simply fit into its *Umwelt*; it is drawn toward it, solicited by it, and exposed to its resistances and surprises.

This dynamic openness is articulated in Merleau-Ponty's notion of *écart*. The *écart* designates the irreducible gap or divergence that structures perception and relation: the distance between body and world, self and other, intention and fulfillment (Merleau-Ponty 1964/2010; Barbaras 2004). Far from being a defect to be eliminated, this gap is the very condition of experience. It is because the world never coincides perfectly with our grasp of it that perception remains

active, exploratory, and meaningful. Behaviour unfolds within this *écart* as a continuous negotiation—an effort to orient oneself within a field that is never fully transparent or mastered.

Read through the combined lenses of *Umwelt*, behaviour, *désir*, and *écart*, Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology reveals a profoundly ecological structure (Toadvine 2009; Abram 1996). The subject is not an isolated consciousness confronting an external world, but a bodily being whose existence consists in maintaining, modulating, and sometimes transforming its relations with a surrounding milieu. Meaning does not arise from representation alone, but from this ongoing tension between belonging and distance, attunement and alterity.

Getting back to electroacoustic practices, it becomes possible to trace a correspondence between this relational phenomenology and the drive behind many recording-based works discussed above, such as *Presque Rien*. The desire—and the consequent care—that moves Ferrari's "extended" ear can be understood as the expression of a behavioural structure of perception that resonates through his full intentionality. The *écart* is precisely what Ferrari seeks to inhabit and momentarily fill: grasping those small sonic events that are normally ignored, and transforming his sound work into something other than a mere search for interesting material. It becomes a situated practice in which the relational dimension of being is central—extended through the use of a device that allows for reconnection: the microphone.

In the field of sound studies and electroacoustic practice, such an ecological orientation finds a particularly fertile resonance, evolving into a conscious use of sound and its technologies not as autonomous objects or ends in themselves, but as means of exploring the relational dimensions of reality: the ways in which beings, environments, and perceptual worlds mutually shape and disclose one another.

A striking example can be found in Toshiya Tsunoda's *Temples recordings*, in which the Japanese sound artist employs a stethoscope equipped with a miniature air microphone fixed to his—or another person's—temple. This device enables him to investigate places of particular significance by placing his own being-there at the centre of the sonic event. The microphone simultaneously registers the internal sounds of the body—heartbeat, circulatory pulsations—and those of the surrounding environment, as well as the interactions between the two, as when the wind strikes his skin or resonates through bodily surfaces. The recording thus becomes a site where corporeality and environment co-produce a sonic field, revealing an intimate ecology of contact, exposure, and mutual affectation.

A similar relational and ecologically attuned orientation underlies the work of Diane Barbé, whose practice centres on the perceptual negotiation between human presence and the acoustic territories of other species. In projects such as *A conference of critters*, where Thailand's rainforests are represented in their human and natural aspects, Barbé approaches recording as a mode of entering into contact with complex ecologies, in a unified view of the human and the extra-human. The microphone here manifests its plural dimension of imitation and extension of our sensory system beyond itself, showing itself capable of offering an externalising view on our relationship to the surrounding - on our behavior, on our *désire*. It modulates Barbé's behaviour by forcing her to adapt her movements, posture, and pace to the rhythms and sensitivities of the species and phenomena she encounters, allowing the recording process itself to become an exercise in shared space and mutual attunement. The human manifests itself together with the microphone as a female voice speaks over the critters ("Oh! I can hear myself!"). In the end the microphone, more than testifying what the artist hears, guides her

listening and relations and helps her developing her sense of care towards sounds and environment. In fact, rather than capturing sounds as isolated signals, Barbé foregrounds the fragile negotiations that make certain sounds possible at all—revealing listening as a form of co-presence, where human perception must accommodate, respect, and sometimes withdraw in order to let other *Umwelten* emerge. In this way, her work expands the phenomenological field beyond intersubjectivity toward a more-than-human relational ecology, reminding to modern ecological conceptions and especially to that of Anna L. Tsing (2015).

Across these diverse practices the ecological implications of a Merleau-Pontian phenomenology are rendered experientially tangible. Each artist treats sound not as an abstract object to be shaped but as a relational field in which bodies, materials, and environments co-constitute one another. The microphone, accordingly, becomes less a neutral capture device than a mediator of encounters, a way of leaning into the world's plurality of modes of being.

5. On aesthetic and ethical stances

These renewed ecological sound practices, situated within the broader field of electroacoustics, reveal a tendency to extend the notion of the aesthetic beyond its modern formulation, as historically instituted since Baumgarten and progressively narrowed through later Kantian and post-Kantian developments (Baumgarten 1750–58; Kant 1790). Rather than centring on the concept of beauty, on the formal codes through which the beautiful is expected to manifest, or ultimately on the qualities of the object produced by *techné*, the ecological approach discussed above mobilises artistic practice as a means of observing the mechanisms of perception in context. In doing so, it reclaims the original sense of *aisthesis*: not aesthetics as a theory of the beautiful, but as a philosophical inquiry into perception itself—without confining this inquiry to the domain of art objects or to normative criteria of aesthetic value—and through that into the sense of our role in the world.

Within this expanded framework, artistic practices are no longer understood primarily as producers of autonomous objects, but as situated modes of inquiry that explore how perception and meaning emerge through concrete relations with environments, materials, and forms of alterity. Aesthetic experience is thus reconfigured as a relational process, inseparable from the contexts—anthropological, sociological, environmental—in which it unfolds (Ingold 2000; Toadvine 2009). *Aisthesis* and the construction of meaning operate here in a virtuous circuit with a specific sense of *place* and *situatedness*, each continuously informing and reshaping the other through artistic practice. When we recognise the correlation between the way we perceive the world and the way in which we shape the world—armed with the consciousness that our environment is the result of a loop of reciprocal influences—the correlation between aesthetic and ethical outcomes becomes evident, and artistic practices in their aesthetic dimension can be understood as what Carmen P. Salgado defined as tools for “reflecting on and opening up other ways of taking action” (Salgado 2024).

It is at this intersection of perception, meaning, and situated relation that an ethical dimension takes shape. The sense of care already identified in the works of Ferrari and Barbé can now be understood as an ethical stance emerging from the interaction of these three poles. This ethics does not arise as a moral prescription imposed from outside the artistic process, but as an immanent consequence of practices that attend to otherness—human and non-human alike—

and that acknowledge the fragility, contingency, and specificity of the relations they engage (Puig de la Bellacasa 2017).

Under this lens, the work of modern and contemporary ecologically oriented electroacoustic practices appears within a complex context, where musical influences intersect with broader fields of speculation and interest, transforming sound into an exploratory methodology and medium rather than an end in itself. A clear and final example is Anne F. Jacques's *Contre-Montagne*, the sonic enquiry of the Carrière Francon in Montreal. Between summer 2024 and winter 2025, the artist visited the 94-hectare quarry several times, carrying recorders, microphones, rope, and battery-powered contraptions. The site, a remnant of the city's construction history—where stones were dug from the ground to build Montreal and the only hill on the island was quarried—had become a snow dump, accumulating half the snow ploughed from city streets each winter. Over time, the site also developed two artificial meltwater lakes of a surprisingly turquoise colour and emerged as a contested and hidden wetland, simultaneously contaminated yet rich in insect and bird biodiversity. The surroundings of the site and the city itself seems to appear and manifest through the sound of the place and not on the side of it, giving a tangible dimension to the exploration narrated. Listening, in the context of such works, becomes an inquiry into how things sound when left to their own devices - on how they keep sounding and thence living-, and into how human perception can situate itself within these modest yet deeply expressive material worlds. More broadly, the work embodies an exploratory attitude that extends beyond sound alone, recognising the full ecological verticality behind the site and the potential of artistic practice to testify, reflect, and intervene, taking action, in the human and more-than-human relations shaping it.

6. References

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